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PROSPECT AND CHALLENGES OF GREEN INDUSTRY DEVELOPMENT IN A DEVELOPING COUNTRY: A CASE STUDY ON BANGLADESH

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Abstract

The green industry is essential for long-term sustainability, both environmentally and economically. This study aims to explore obstacles and benefits for establishing green industry. This paper also attempts to raise awareness among government and industry owners about the importance of the green industry. This study reveals that the green industry has played a vital role in future long-run economic, social, and environmental benefits. However, lack of awareness, poor economic conditions, lack of government support, and unclear national policy have remained the significant barriers to entrepreneurs establishing green industries in Bangladesh. Although the government of Bangladesh has given some financial assistance to establish a sustainable industry, it is not enough to adequately fulfill the needs of such an industry. Finally, this study also provides pragmatic recommendations to foster green industry development in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Green industry, Sustainability, SDG, 4R, LEED, BEER, Bangladesh

1. Background of the study

Bangladesh's Ready Made Garments (RMG) industry has played a significant role in the economy, which has provided benefits to the socioeconomic development in the country, especially has created many employment opportunities, reducing poverty and increasing the quality of life (Zohir (2001)). This sector contributes 9.25 percent of the total GDP; RMG export earnings amount to 42.61 billion USD,

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and employment generation is 4.22 million (Bangladesh Bank, 2023). This sector has already taken many social and economic sustainability initiatives, but environmental sustainability needs to be considered more (GIZ, 2020).

Ecological degradation has been a significant problem in industrial sectors over the past 30 years (Damayanti et al., 2021). Moreover Liu et al. (2018) described that, industries are major contributors to environmental degradation through air and water pollution, solid waste generation, and deforestation, and understanding the sources and impacts of this pollution is crucial for developing effective strategies to mitigate its effects. On the other hand, the level of industrial activity is related to economic development; hence consumption of energy and emission will rise with the level of development. Moreover, Ahuti (2015) also suggested that industrial development creates environmental degradation, resource depletion, social exploitation, and economic recklessness. Suppose the average temperature of our planet's surface increases by 2 degree Celsius, affecting staggering environmental changes, rapidly rising sea levels, withering crops, diminishing water reserves, drought, cyclones, and floods (global warming of 1.5 degree Celsius, 2018). However, the green industry can prevent environmental damage from industrial development by ensuring development without environmental harm. Therefore, the green industry is committed to protecting and restoring the environment, ensuring the balance of the ecosystem.

Bangladesh has been striving towards industrial reform in the modern era of globalization with aspirations of achieving middle-income status (Reza et al., 2017). In this regard, the Bangladesh RMG industry has taken the green initiative to become a more sustainable sector. Therefore, the competitiveness of the Bangladeshi industry is also largely determined by the type of resources used and the value chain compared to its peers. The green industry is a prerequisite for long terms competitiveness and sustainability (Reza et al., 2017). Green transformation can increase not only competitiveness but also sustainability. Therefore, RMG industries are now adopting green principles to address this environmental risk and long-term sustainability, thus, increasing competitiveness (BGMEA, 2022).

Although the green industry is environmentally friendly, transforming the green industry is highly expensive. According to BKMEA (2022), green industry is ten times more expensive than the conventional industry; thus, entrepreneurs needs help for managing this significant

capital to construct a green industry. Moreover, at the initial stage, green industry establishment needs more capital than conventional industry. Furthermore, entrepreneurs need a functional bank loan for green industry construction. Although the green industry is urgently needed for sustainable development, Bangladesh's policymakers should emphasise it more. Even entrepreneurs need to be made aware of the benefit of the green industry as they think the traditional industry is easier to set up than the green industry.

This study will reveal the importance of the green industry for economic and environmental sustainability and achieving sustainable development goals. This study will also be helpful for policymakers to make more environmentally friendly policies as well as support green industry development and also for environmental sustainability.

2. Methodology and Data Sources:

This study provided an overview and analysis of the green building industry, with a specific focus on the certification process and its impact on various industries, particularly the Ready-Made Garments (RMG) sector. The research utilized a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods to gather and analyze data.

The primary data source for this study was the U.S. Green Building Council (USGBC), which served as a comprehensive repository of information on green building practices, certifications, and industry trends. Country-wise data selection is conducted using reliable sources such as government reports, industry publications, and reputable research organizations to ensure a comprehensive analysis of different regions. Additionally, specific data related to the green building industry in Bangladesh is obtained from government reports, industry associations, and local research studies focusing on sustainable construction practices and certifications. The collected data was segregated based on industries and building types to gain a comprehensive understanding of the impact of green building certifications.

The study focused on LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design) as a widely recognized green building certification system, specifically LEED version 4. Detailed information on LEED version 4, including criteria, rating system, and requirements for new construction projects, is gathered from the USGBC website. Four case studies are conducted to illustrate the impact of green building certifications on different industries. These case studies analyze the certification process, benefits derived from certification, and challenges faced during implementation.

The research paper aims to accomplish the following two main objectives:

To investigate the barriers and challenges encountered by entrepreneurs in establishing green industries within Bangladesh's RMG sector. Additionally, assess the level of awareness among government officials, policymakers, and industry stakeholders regarding the significance of the green industry.

Provide practical recommendations to facilitate the growth of the green industry in Bangladesh by addressing the identified challenges and maximizing the potential economic, social, and environmental benefits associated with implementing sustainable practices in the RMG sector.

3. Interlink between green industry and environment sustainability

Environmental sustainability is the core pillar to addressing the unprecedented ecological challenges. Contrarily, industrialization degrades the environment while bringing economic accessibility and social security. Industrialization should consider the people-profit-planet (3P) concept, which advocates for the green industry initiative. Maltzman & Shirley (2011) described that green building is usually associated with the structure and implementation of environmentally responsible and resource-efficient processes in a building's life-cycle from design, construction, operation, maintenance, and renovation to demolition.

Robert Goodland defines environmental sustainability as maintaining natural capital connected to social and economic sustainability. Moreli (2011) explained that sustainability requires that current economic activity not disproportionately burden future generations. Green building practices can substantially reduce or eliminate negative environmental impacts through high-performance design, construction, and operation practices that lead the market. Barbier (2012) defined the green industry as a pathway toward sustainability. The United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) indicates that green industry is "industrial production and development that does not come at the expense of the health of natural systems or lead to adverse human health outcomes." At the industrial level, this involves "greening" existing industries and establishing new 'green' sectors.

4. Synergies between LEED and SDG

Bangladesh's government has committed to achieving SDG by "2030," so the government has taken various initiatives to meet the targeted goals, especially on environmental sustainability. Bangladesh's government has considered to making the business sector green. The government supports entrepreneurs for going green and achieving Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) certification authorized by USGBC (United State Green Building Council). LEED is the world's most widely used green building rating system and provides a framework for healthy, highly efficient, and cost-efficient green buildings. Although there are various certification types in the world based on different Indicators, "LEED certification," is a globally recognized symbol of "sustainability achievement". There are many synergies between LEED and the SDGs. Below, the synergies are discussed; (source; www.usgbc.org)

4.1 Environmental synergies:

SDG goal 6 requires clean water and sanitation. In LEED v4.1 building design and construction (BD+C), outdoor water use reduction, indoor water use reduction and building level water metering are required prerequisites for Certification. In addition, LEED zero energy and zero carbon certifications recognize the achievement of net zero goals in building operations by maximizing energy efficiency and implementing renewable energy, which meets SDG goal 7 (Affordable and clean energy). On the other hand, reversing the contribution of buildings to global climate change is a core goal in LEED, with ways to ensure that project sites are safe for human activity and "respect the unique conditions of surrounding areas," considering "SDG goals 13 and 15;". Green Building can directly contribute to SDG Goals, such as "Good health and well-being" (goal 3); the rating system's indoor environmental quality credit category is dedicated to protecting the health and comfort of "building occupants," LEED emphasizes the human experience and pushes project teams to create spaces that reduce carbon emissions and address "SDG 10 goals," (Reduce inequality within Countries). Lastly, Innovation credits in LEED, reward projects for community outreach and engagement cover "SDG 17 goals;" -Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development.

4.2 Social Synergies:

Green buildings ensure that the rating system's indoor environmental quality credit category is dedicated to protecting the health and comfort of "building occupants," directly related to SDG goal 3. LEEDV4 emphasizes not only reducing carbon emissions but also addressing "SDG 10 goals," (Reduce inequality within among Countries). Lastly, Innovation credits in LEED reward projects for "community outreach and engagement," cover "SDG 17 goals;" - Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development.

4.3 Economic synergies:

By installing solar panels, building resilient infrastructure covers SDG 8 and 9 goals. The new LEED for cities and communities rating system is directly connected to the purposes of SDG 11. Besides that, improving the responsible production and consumption of materials supports SDG 12.

5. Benefits of green industry

Bangladesh is one of those developing countries where sustainability has thrived alongside economic growth, as sustainability issues have been embedded in long-term plans. The country has committed to transforming SDG awareness (2030 agenda) (Islam et al., 2020). To achieve the SDG goal, it is necessary to prevent environmental damage from industrial development. The green industry is environmentally friendly (Damayanti et al., 2021) because this industry is not as harmful to the environment and health as traditional industries.

The green industry can improve a country's socioeconomic development and provides favorable condition for sustainable industrial development. On the other hand, Tariq (2016) identified that green employee empowerment is the key to enhancing an organization's outcome, where employees are motivated to pursue green goals more effectively and efficiently. Calza et al. (2017) explained that companies are changing their attitudes not only because they are forced by national and international laws or pressure from consumers but also because adopting environmental management strategies creates opportunities for business organizations.

5.1 Social benefit:

Green Industry refers to a business that operates in an environmentally friendly manner, offering numerous social benefits. The Green Industry creates new job opportunities in various fields, including renewable energy, green construction, and waste management (Lombardi, 2015). These jobs provide stable employment for individuals while also promoting economic growth and development. Furthermore, the green industry firmly commits to community development, investing in local infrastructure and supporting community-based initiatives which help to build stronger and more resilient communities, focusing on sustainability and social responsibility (D & Scherp 2018). Additionally, the green industry can improve public health by reducing pollution and promoting healthy living through access to green spaces and sustainable transportation options, leading to improved physical and mental well-being for individuals and communities.

5.2 Economic benefit:

Green industry also increases economic benefits through money savings. For example, energy efficiency leads to lower energy consumption, which positively affects a company's overall profitability. Von wezsacker (2009) shows that clean technologies typically have relatively short periods and lead to lower annual costs. After an initial cost, these investments help reduce resource consumption while generating more money through increased productivity. This savings funding can further support business expansion or job growth, thereby driving economic resource consuming.

5.3 Environmental benefit:

Green industry can reduce resource consumption by making maximum efficient use of the potential of natural capital. This is particularly beneficial as it off sets any inefficiency in the system and reduce waste. Improved resource efficiency, i.e. using energy, materials and water more effectively, allows resources to be conserved (Reza et al 2017). Moreover, peck and Chipman (2007) suggested that green follows the 3 R (Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle) principle. Using raw materials more efficiently can reduce the demand for raw materials. For example, recycling waste materials into industrial production reduces the need to extract and process natural resources. For instance, in the textile industry, recycling water saves water and reduces the need for more water. Finally, using

green technology will reduce the negative impact on the environment.

Figure 1: Environmental benefits of green industry

Source: GIZ, (2020)

6. Obstacle of green industry

Nowadays, environmental liabilities are beginning to represent real economic risks, and environmental legislation in many developing countries is rapidly converging, following the path of industrialized countries. Islam et al. (2014) addressed that environmental awareness and regulations were either absent or there was a lack of enforcement in developing countries in the past. In 2015, it was considered a historical turning point in combating climate change. Although the United Nations has established the Agenda 2030 for steady development, the world's first global climate agreement has not yet been reached. Similarly, there is some obstacle to establishing a green industry.

6.1 Economic obstacle:

Green industry setup requires additional cost than traditional industry, so economic instability is a significant obstacle to making green industry. Bohdanowicz (2006) identified that installing technologies to ensure green practices is highly costly. On the other hand, the lack of reasonable profit from green manufacturing is demotivated industry owners from establishing green industry. The industry owners need more financial stability to carry out the initial cost.

6.2 Policy obstacle:

A clear policy framework is needed to develop the green industry in Bangladesh. Khan & Shammi (2022) identified three major obstacles to establishing a green industry-

6.2.1 Inadequate regularity and institutional frameworks:

There is a lack of clarity and consistency in the regularity framework, which makes it difficult for business to navigate and comply with regulations related to environmental protection and sustainable development.

6.2.2 Limited access to financing and technical assistance:

Green industry development often face difficulties in accessing finance and technical assistance due to lack of specialized institutions and the absence of dedicated funding mechanisms.

6.2.3 Limited public awareness and stakeholder engagement:

There is a lack of public awareness and stakeholder engagement regarding the benefits and opportunities of the Green Industry variations in standards international and national.

By addressing these obstacles and developing a supportive policy environment, Bangladesh can unlock the potential of the green industry to contribute to sustainable development and economic growth. Moreover, Akther (2021) also described that green building techniques could prove advantageous if a diversified plan can be developed to gain benefits.

6.3 Management obstacle:

Green industry management refers to producing goods or generating services using strategies, technologies and workplace practices that aim to reduce industrial waste, minimize pollution, recycle waste, do paperless operations, and produce environmental-friendly products

and services (Mohiuddin & Al-Amin (2022)). Although the Green industry is different in many ways, like building design, site selection, construction, material and technological use, it shows that green industry management is also different from traditional industry. At the same time, lack of knowledge of the green industry is another obstacle to developing the green industry in Bangladesh. Khodadadzadeha (2017) reported that there needed to be more sustainable knowledge for making green industry. Hwang & tan (2012) found different challenges encountered by project managers who execute green construction projects. They also determined the critical knowledge issues necessary to respond to such challenges.

7. LEED Rating System and Version 4

There are various certification types in the world based on different Indicators, such as Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED), Higg, Arc and Pearl. LEED is the world's most widely used green building rating system; LEED provides a framework for healthy, highly efficient, and cost-saving green buildings. LEED certification is a globally recognized symbol of sustainability achievement and leadership. This rating system is applicable for new and existing construction. This rating system is continuing its update process based on time and environmental considerations, and each updated version ensures more environment-friendly construction by its checklist. LEED started its journey in 2000, by version 1.0 category, as the first version it was a pilot version. The end of 2000, version 2.0 was established after completing the pilot phase. After that, version 3.0 was updated in 2007. Moreover, the version 3.0 checklist was more advanced with environment-friendly prerequisites than version 2. Similarly, in 2013 the newest version, 4.0 and then the 4.1 version in 2018, which is time bound for eliminating unprecedented environmental challenges by industry. On the other hand, the intent is to promote healthy, durable, affordable, and environmentally sound practices in building design and construction (Green Building Design and Construction guideline, 2019).

Figure 2: LEED version.

Source: USGBC, (2023)

Above chart shows that, most recently maximum of the green industry has been developed under version 4.0. Here are the version 4.0 prerequisite details-

Prerequisites of the LEED Green Building Rating systems address 7 topics-

7.1 Location and Transportation (LT):

The Location and Transportation (LT) category rewards thoughtful decisions about building location with credits encouraging compact development, alternative transportation, and connection with amenities like restaurants and parks. The LT category is an outgrowth of the sustainable sites, which formerly covered location-related topics.

7.2 Sustainable Sites (SS):

The Sustainable Sites (SS) category rewards decisions about the environment surrounding the building with credits that emphasize the vital relationships among buildings, ecosystems, and ecosystem services. It focuses on restoring project site elements, integrating the site with local and regional ecosystems, and preserving the biodiversity that natural systems rely on.

7.3 Water Efficiency (WE):

The Water Efficiency (WE) section addresses water holistically, looking at indoor use, outdoor use, specialized uses, and metering. The section is based on an “efficiency first” approach to water conservation. As a result, each prerequisite looks at water efficiency and reductions in potable water use alone. Then, the WE credits additionally recognize the benefit of no potable and alternative water sources.

7.4 Energy and atmosphere (EA):

The Energy and Atmosphere (EA) category approaches energy holistically, addressing energy use reduction, energy-efficient design strategies, and renewable energy sources. Energy efficiency in a green building starts with a focus on design that reduces overall energy needs, such as building orientation, glazing selection, and the choice of climate-appropriate building materials.

7.5 Materials and Resources (MR):

The Materials and Resources (MR) credit category focuses on minimizing the embodied energy and other impacts associated with the extraction, processing, transport, maintenance, and disposal of building materials. The requirements support a life-cycle approach that improves performance and promotes resource efficiency. Each condition identifies a specific action that fits into the larger context of a life-cycle approach to embodied impact reduction.

7.6 Indoor Environmental Quality (EQ):

The Indoor Environmental Quality (EQ) category rewards decisions made by project teams about indoor air quality and thermal, visual, and acoustic comfort. Green buildings with good indoor environmental quality protect the health and comfort of building occupants. High-quality indoor environments also enhance productivity, decrease absenteeism, improve the building’s value, and reduce liability for building designers and owners.

7.7 Innovation (IN):

Sustainable design strategies and measures constantly improve. New technologies are continually introduced to the marketplace and up-to-date scientific research influences building design strategies. This LEED category recognizes projects for innovative building features and sustainable building practices and processes.

8. Green building (LEED) status of Bangladesh in RMG competitive countries

Figure 3: Green Building Status in RMG competitive countries

Source: USGBC, (2023)

The above data shows India is leading with 2659 LEED-registered buildings, and Spain holds second with 1298 buildings. Besides, Turkey and Italy have the remaining third and fourth positions with 1188 and 1131 LEED-buildings. On the other hand, Bangladesh holds the fifth position, where 731 Green buildings along with the majority of industrial buildings has been registered under LEED platform. After that, Vietnam (336), Indonesia (73), and Cambodia (30) stand in sixth, seventh and eighth position, respectively.

9. Bangladesh Government initiative for the green industry

Green building is an essential solution for people, organizations, and businesses, helping to minimize the negative impacts of life and production processes on the environment (Weng et al., 2018). Bangladesh's government has taken the initiative to make the business sector green. In addition, Bangladesh Bank provides loans up to BDT 20 Crore for green industry development purposes. Additionally, there is a separate loan facility for solar systems and

biogas plant instalments (Bangladesh Bank, 2021). The government has also provides a duty free facility for the import of green products. The government provided green loan facilities to entrepreneurs. For example, the green transformation fund supports industry owners in transforming existing or new industries into green ones. This fund is dedicated to specific green materials like renewable energy, alternative energy, solid and liquid waste management, 3R implementation, and eco-friendly brick production. It also provides supports for overall green establishment materials. In 2016, Bangladesh Bank created a long-term refinancing of USD 200 million. The fund is available for all export-oriented sectors to support the transition to a greener economy and ensure sustainable export growth.

Figure 4: Sector-wise Total Green Finance

Source: Bangladesh Bank, (2022)

Moreover, Bangladesh bank has a scheme for green finance to make a smoother green business and ensure the maximum support to entrepreneurs. During Fiscal Year 2020-21, banks disbursed BDT 97.64 billion, and Non-Bank Financial Institutes (NBFIs) disbursed BDT 3.1 billion. Details are given in the below table respectively.

Table 1: Green Finance in FY2021 (million BDT)

Types of banks / NBFIs	Renewable energy	Energy efficiency	Alternative energy	Liquid waste management	Solid waste management	Recycling manufacturing and recyclable goods	Environment friendly brick production	Green Environment friendly Establishment	Green agriculture	Green CM SME	Green SR F	Total
SOCBs	1838.8	227.9	0.0	396.1	119.1	813.5	372.1	5638.7	56.6	93.9	0.0	9557.0
SDBs	6.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.0	0.0	2.8	0.0	0.0	20.2
PCBs	1598.04	11014.1	45.5	6074.6	177.8	10294.4	5438.6	36893.8	498.4	469.5	68.4	72573.5
FCBs	3.1	1264.3	0.0	559.8	0.0	3.4	0.0	12993.7	462.2	200.2	0.0	15486.9
Banks total	344644	12506.3	45.5	7030.6	296.9	11111.4	5821.7	55526.2	1020.1	763.7	68.45	97637.7
NBFIs	496.7	1032.2	0.0	379.6	83.1	0.3	312.1	100.0	157.4	516.8	77.9	3156.3
Grand total	3943.1	13538.5	45.5	7410.3	380.0	11111.7	6133.8	55626.2	1177.5	1280.5	146.3	100794.0

Source: Bangladesh Bank, 2022

The government also created a revolving refinance scheme of BDT 2.0 billion in 2009, intending to broaden finance for green products or initiatives at a lower cost of funds, which subsequently increased to BDT 4.0 billion.

10. Current situation of green building in Bangladesh

Bangladesh is the third RMG exporter country in the world. Nowadays, approximately 4500 RMG industries have already been established in the country (BKMEA, 2023), whether around 600 (13.33%) registered green RMG industries including 270 building are LEED certified (USGBC, 2023). The percentage of green industry is not satisfactory compared to other competitive countries. However, Bangladesh RMG sector has beginning a new era of a sustainable business environment. Moreover, Enomoto et al. (2019) stated that the entrepreneurs of Bangladesh's RMG industries have already considered the "Go Green" concept. Bangladeshi RMG industries are

situated in just a few districts of Bangladesh, grouped into three regions – Dhaka, Narayanganj and Chattogram.

Figure 5: Region-wise green Building (USGBC, 2023)

Source: USGBC, (2023)

The above data shows that there are 731 Green Buildings (LEED registered) established in the country till October 2023 (USGBC, 2023). Whether 204 industries are achieved LEED certification. In addition, most of the green building has established in the Dhaka zone, which holds 558 out of 731. Besides that, Narayanganj and Chattogram holds 89 and 67 green buildings. In addition, 17 buildings are located in Tangail, Hobiganj, Barishal and Khulna districts. Moreover USGBC reported that, in Bangladesh majority of green buildings are RMG industry. Most recently, Green Textile Limited (unit - 4) has achieved LEED platinum certification with a 104 score and has become the top LEED woven industry in the world.

11. Environmental benefits of green RMG industry: Case study

Table 2: Comparison of green RMG industry (Out of 110) Version-4.0

Category	Platinum	Gold	Silver	Certified
Unite Name	Green Textile Limited, Unit-4	Metro knitting and dying ltd.	Pentagon Knit com and global apparel park	Flaxen Dress maker
Location and	15/20	13/20	13/20	7/20

Transportation (LT)				
Sustainable Sites (SS)	10/10	9/10	3/10	7/10
Water Efficiency (WE)	11/11	9/11	8/11	9/11
Energy and Atmosphere (EA)	32/33	18/33	18/33	8/33
Material and Resources (MR)	11/13	5/13	2/13	2/13
Indoor Environmental Quality (EQ)	14/16	1/16	2/16	0/16
Innovation (IN)	6/6	5/6	5/6	2/6
Integrative Process (IE) (Additional)	1/1	1/1	0	1/1
Regional Priority (RP) (Additional)	4/4	4/4	2/4	4/4
Total Score	104	65	53	40

11.1 Green Textile Limited (Unit-4):

Green Textile Limited (unit-4) is Bangladesh's most recent and highest point holder Platinum LEED Certified industry and also the world's top-ranked woven Industry. This Industry awarded 104 points and achieved LEED platinum certification in version 4. The project size is 54,000 sq ft and industry is located at Mymensingh. This Industry is highly recognized for taking leadership in energy and environment design.

The main intention of industry management is to reduce energy and water consumption. This Industry reduces 96.96% of energy consumption by using green energy instead of fossil fuel, 100% water consumption, reusing and recycling 84.61% of waste material, and ensuring the majority use of natural resources. This Industry provides 75% of no-harm activity during selecting the location and using transportation for construction purposes. Management hopes this certification will bring maximum worker satisfaction and increase efficiency and production.

11.2 Metro Knitting and Dying Ltd:

The industry is located in Narayanganj, Bangladesh, and the project size is 287,328 sq ft. industry management has committed to continuing the sustainable go-green concept in its factory area. In considering sustainable industrial development, this unit achieved USGBC-certified LEED Gold in the version 4 category in May 2022. This company achieves significant benchmarks in terms of LEED credits. This industry achieves 90% improvement in sustainable site development and 54.54% in energy savings. Not only that, this building saves 81.81% of water by applying the 4R method. Moreover this premises has reduces 100% of water consumption by landscaping water, 40% baseline indoor water consumption and 50% wastewater generation through the Green Building Information Gateway. According to the opinion of the management level of this company, workers are delighted with their activities. Most importantly, they have found appreciation from the workers due to the availability of chillers which keep the temperature down in their working section.

11.3 Pentagon Knit com and global apparel Park:

Pentagon knit com, and global apparel park, is the LEED silver certified Industry, by version 4, located in Tongi, Gazipur, Bangladesh. The project size is 158,455 square feet. This industry awarded LEED certification from USGBC on October 27, 2021. This

factory reduced 54.54% energy consumption by setting energy star electrical equipment. In addition, industry reduces 72.72% of water use by using the water-efficient fixture and applying the 4R method in industrial premises. Besides that, this Industry reuses 15.38% of material resources and saves 30% of environmental consideration on its premises. Workers' satisfaction and increase of production capacity is the significant achievement of this factory.

11.4 Flaxen Dress Maker Ltd:

Flaxen dress maker Ltd started its journey on August 10, 2021. This industry achieved LEED certification in the version 4 category. The factory management planned to manage this certification with careful environmental management and by following the 4R principles in their premises. This building reduces energy consumption by 24.24% and water consumption 81.81% by using efficient technology and the 4R method. In addition, the industry premises ensure that 70% of the area is environmentally friendly.

The above 4 certification levels are the same as the version 4 category but different in certification level, which refers to different types of environmental conservation; in platinum-rated certified Industry, Green Textile Ltd. Unit-4 achieves 104 out of 110, which is more environmentally friendly than metro knitting and dyeing Ltd which is awarded Gold certification by earning 65 points. Similarly, the above table shows that pentagon Knit com and global apparel park achieved 53 points out of 110 and silver certification by addressing less environment-friendly industries than Gold-certified ones. After that, a LEED-certified Industry named Flaxen Dress maker Ltd earned 40 points out of 100 and referring to more environment-friendly Industries than non-green industries.

12. Conclusion

This paper explores the necessity of the Green Industry from the perspective of achieving economic and environmental sustainability. Bangladesh already gains its success through rapid industrialization from RMG Industry, but there should be an environmental concern on industrial development. Although the Bangladesh government has taken the initiative to make the business sector green, provided supports are not up to level. Therefore, industry owners are less interested in the green industry setup. However, the world is in an alarming situation due to global warming, so every industrial development initiatives must consider its impact on environment. Bangladesh's government should take the necessary steps to foster

green industry development in Bangladesh. This study suggested some recommendations to support the government and policy maker foster green industry development. The recommendations are;

- The government of Bangladesh should develop and implement sustainable policies and implement their own rating system named BEER (Building Energy Efficiency & Environment) and promote the adoption of green technologies, eco-friendly manufacturing processes, and sustainable practices in all sectors.
- The government should provide incentives for textile and garment factories that adopt eco-friendly production practices, such as reducing water usage, waste reduction, and use of renewable energy.
- The government can update environmental regulations and perform proper execution to ensure that industries and individuals comply with sustainable practices and reduce environmental impact.
- The government should establish a price negotiation framework for buyers, as green and non-green manufacturing products should be treated separately.
- Bangladesh Bank should make more flexible green loan facilities for industry owners. In addition, Bangladesh bank should enhance proper monitoring of green industry loans like green transformation funds, refinance schemes for environment-friendly products, and other green support funds.

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